

A STUDY OF AWARENESS AND UTILIZATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA BY B.ED TRAINEES

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Abstract:

The present study aims to study of awareness and utilization of social media by B.Ed trainees. The present study the investigator adapted simple random sampling technique the size of the sample of 300 B.Ed College Trainees in Villupuram District of Tamil Nadu State. The Social Media Awareness scale- constructed by the R. Bakkiyaraj and the social media utilization scale- constructed by the R. Bakkiyaraj .The result shows that there is a positive relationship between Social Media Awareness scale and the social media utilization scale.

Introduction:

Social media is a phrase being tossed around a lot these days. Media is an instrument on communication, like a newspaper or a radio, so social media would be a social instrument of communication Social media can be defined as "interactive platforms via which individuals and communities create and share user-generated content". Social Networking has become very popular during the past few years, but it can still be very difficult to understand for someone new to social networking. The open-ended nature of social networks add to this. Once signed onto a social network, having answered a few basic profile questions, it is easy to sit back and wonder what we are supposed to do next.

Need and Significance of the Study:

Currently, the use of social media appears to be in its momentum stage; changing the styles, and patterns of communication at macro, as well as micro level. The assertion that social media "...can provide ways for people to interact both within and outside the spatial bounds of the event" is supported by some international events, like London Riots (2011), change of Libyan and Egyptian Rule (2011) etc. Such media acts as a vehicle for disseminating critical information and promoting access to the information. Social media seems to have a greater impact on education, particularly higher education by creating and promoting virtual learning environments for augmenting distributed learning. Learners thus formulate their virtual communities and interact freely with each other. They can exchange their learning experiences, research findings and academic opportunities. The use and benefits of social media particularly for academic gains appears to be an area of interest for many researchers in education and social sciences. Different researchers have addressed different areas of using social media at various academic and social levels. Hence, the investigator decided to take this study to know the Awareness and Utilization of Social Media by B.Ed Trainees.

Objective: To find out whether there is any significant relationship between Social Media Awareness and Utilization of Social Media for the Trainees of B.Ed., College.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between Social Media Awareness and Utilization of Social Media of the Trainees of B.Ed College.

Method of the Study: For the present investigation the investigator adapted normative survey as a method.

Sample of the Study: The present study the investigator adapted simple random sampling technique the size of the sample of 300 B.Ed College Trainees in Villupuram District of Tamil Nadu State.

Tools Used: The following tools were used

- The Social Media Awareness scale- constructed by the R. BAKKIYARAJ (2013).

Statistical Techniques: In this present investigation Correlation analysis technique was used

Correlation Analysis:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between Awareness and Utilization of Social Media by the students of Engineering, Agriculture and Teacher Education. In order to test the above Hypothesis 'r' value is calculated.

Relationship between relationship between Awareness and Utilization of Social Media

Variables	N	'r' value	Level of Significance at 0.5 level
Awareness and Utilization of Social Media	300	0.210	Significant

From the above table, since the 'r' value is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the Null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is a Positive relationship between Awareness and Utilization of Social Media.

Recommendations:

- The present study gives analysis about the Awareness and Utilization of Social Media by the students of Teacher Education. Based on the important findings stated earlier the following recommendations are suggested for the betterment.
- There is significant relationship found between Social Media Awareness and Social media utilization among Engineering, Teacher Education and Agriculture students, hence to increase Social media utilization among Engineering, Teacher Education and Agriculture students, Social media awareness should be created among the students.
- Higher education institutions can add social media utilization as a separate activity to enhance socialization.
- The students should be encouraged to use Social Media for educational purposes.

Conclusion:

The present study made on Awareness and Utilization of Social Media by the students of Teacher Education”. Hence activities are to be included in higher educational curriculum to increase Social media awareness and utilization. More researches are to be conducted in this field to increase cautious and useful utilization of Social media.

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